

LIFESTYLE AND LIVING CONDITIONS FACTORS THAT AFFECT THE DISEASE OF CHILDREN UNDER THE AGE OF SEVEN

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Relevance of the study. The health of children and their upbringing and development have always been of great importance in the world. According to the World Health Organization, 140 million children are born in the world every year, of which an average of 5 million die before reaching the age of 5. The countries with the highest mortality rates are the Central African countries, with a mortality rate of 115 per 1,000 births (Nigeria 112, Somalia 107, Chad 105), while in Uzbekistan it is 14.1 (<https://childmortality.org/analysis>).

A kind of "barometer" of the level of socio-economic development of the country, one of the main criteria for assessing the health of the population is the structure and level of childhood morbidity. The health of children up to the age of seven is important for the birth of a healthy child, a healthy generation, and for their upbringing and upbringing, because raising children to a healthy age and creating a healthy workforce is a guarantee of the future health of the population and the development of the country (2, p. 18; 3, p. 19-25).

In our Republic, maternal and child health protection is one of the priority socio-political directions of our state. In recent years, our state and government have been carrying out many positive works to protect and further improve the health of mothers and children, and to increase the scope, quality and efficiency of medical and social assistance provided to them (1 p. 24; 9, p. 10 - 12; 10, p. 30 - 32).

In our country, along with the establishment of highly qualified specialized medical centers for mothers and children, the restructuring of primary medical and sanitary care institutions, the establishment of departments of mothers-obstetricians-gynecologists and children-pediatricians in central polyclinics that provide assistance to mothers and children, indicate that attention has been further increased to maintaining their health. Nevertheless, in order to implement high-quality and effective medical care in the republic, the study of the health of children of preschool age, the early identification of biological and socio-hygienic aspects of the causes of children's illnesses, risk factors, their elimination and the

development of measures based on a comprehensive systematic approach to improving their health, quality, is one of the urgent issues of the day. (10, p. 30-33; 5, p. 334; 6, p. 334).

The purpose of the research: to comprehensively assess the medical and social factors that affect preschool children's illness, to develop a set of measures aimed at improving children's health and the quality of medical care.

Research material and methods. Andijan region is located in the eastern part of Fergana valley. The area is 4.2 thousand km². The population is 3 million 166 thousand people (2021). Andijan region has 14 rural districts (Andijan, Asaka, Baliqchi, Buloqboshi, Boz, Jalakuduq, Izboskan, Marhamat, Oltinkol, Pakhtaabad, Ulug'nor, Khojaabad, Shahrikhan, Korgantepa), 11 cities (Andijan, Asaka, Marhamat, Okhunboboev, Pakhtaabad, Poitug', Khanabad, Khojaabad, Shahrikhan, Karasuv, Kurgantepa), 5 towns (Andijan, Boz, South Olamushuk, Kuyganor, Polvontosh) and 888 community groups (2021). Center - Andijan sh. Uzbeks make up the majority of the population. The population density is on average 517 people per 1 km².

Results and conclusions. Respondents who rated maternal care as good were 1.5 times more likely to be in urban areas than in rural areas, while those who rated it as unsatisfactory were 17.0% in urban areas and 24.5% in rural areas.

The existence of a correlation between children's morbidity and living conditions has also been reported in a number of similar studies [56,74]. Family living (home) conditions have a direct impact on the health of family members and are of great importance in medicine and health care as a factor that triggers the development of certain diseases. Therefore, every medical worker, especially doctors involved in preventive work, should be able to correctly assess the living conditions of the family and, drawing appropriate conclusions, develop measures to prevent diseases.

Our study showed that the lower the quality of housing conditions, the higher the incidence of childhood diseases. It was noted that the risk of illness in children with poor housing conditions was 3.5 times higher than in children with good housing conditions. Among rural families, 11.0% rated housing conditions as "bad" and 9.0% in urban areas, while those who rated them as "good" were 20.0% and 23.0%, respectively.

It is clear from this that while the impact of some risk factors decreases with increasing age, the impact of this factor does not lose its strength at all ages of children.

The fight against smoking is as important for children as it is for adults in the formation of a healthy lifestyle and prevention of diseases. If parental smoking affects children's health from the period of pregnancy, then after birth, babies immediately become passive smokers, and the impact of this harmful habit is even stronger. It was found that the risk of illness in children in families with smokers is 3 times higher than in families without smokers. 13.0% of parents in rural areas and 18.0% in urban areas have harmful habits.

One of the factors that negatively affects the health of children is the psychological state in the family or the relationship between family members. To assess the psychological state, we divided all the families in which the social survey was conducted into 2 groups: Group 1 - families with a satisfactory psychological state and relationships in the family, that is, families with a father and a mother, good relationships between them, and no harmful habits among family members.

If there is no parent in the family, or if there are frequent disagreements and conflicts between them, or if one of the family members is addicted to harmful habits, we classified such families as group 2, that is, with unsatisfactory family relationships and poor mental health. In families with unsatisfactory mental health, the risk of children getting sick is 3 times higher than in families with satisfactory mental health, 17.0% in rural areas and 25.0% in urban areas. In particular, in urban areas, the mental health is 1.5 times more unsatisfactory than in rural areas.

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